

Substituted Aliphatic Amines as Possible Pressor Active Agents

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Manuscript received 20 September 1975; revised 2 December 1975, accepted 6 December 1975

OUR continued interest in cyanoethylation reactions has prompted us to synthesize some substituted amines. The biological activity of aliphatic amines and its therapeutic use as pressor active and antispasmodic agents is well documented. In this direction Berger and Dole¹ have shown that pressor activity is influenced by the presence of terminal amino groups, Dunker and Hartung² also made a thorough review of the literature of amines. Rohrmann and Shoule have studied the aliphatic amines for pressor action and also determined the correlation of the structure of amines with pressor activity.

In the present study attempts have been made to prepare some aliphatic amines. Here some cyanoethylated compounds so synthesized, have been subjected to reduction^{4,5,6} to produce corresponding amines which have amino group at the terminal carbon atom. The results of some amines are shown, whereas pharmacological screening of the remaining compounds is under study.

Experimental

Malonodimethylamide: A mixture of ethylmalonate (10g, 0.062 mol), methylamine (16g, 25%) and 0.1g of sodium hydride was shaken at 0° until it was homogeneous. It was kept at room temperature for 12 hr. and then heated on a water bath for 1 hr. The solid mass was crystallized from benzene. The Malonamides were characterized by their sharp melting points and analyses (Table 1).

α,α -bis (β -cyanoethyl) malonodimethylamide: To a well stirred solution of malonodimethylamide (3g, 0.023ml) in dioxane (20 ml) and Triton B (1 g), freshly distilled acrylonitrile (3g, 0.056 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 4 hr. It was acidified with dil. HCl and poured in ice water and extracted with ethylene dichloride. After removing the solvent, the solid mass was crystallized and had sharp melting points and analysis (Table 2).

α,α -bis (3-aminopropyl) malonodimethylamide: A solution α,α -bis (β -cyanoethyl) malonodimethylamide (4.72 g, 0.02 mol) in tetrahydrofuran was added dropwise to a suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (1.52g) in tetrahydrofuran. The solution was refluxed for 2 hr and lithium aluminium hydride was decomposed. After removing the solvent, the residual mass left behind, was crystallized from ethyl alcohol. The aminopropyl malonamides were characterized by their sharp melting points and analyses (Tables 3,4).

The preparation of substituted α cyano, α, α , bis (β -cyanoethyl) (R) amides has been described in our previous communication.

Pharmacological Studies: Since many aliphatic amines have been reported to possess considerable pressor activity³, therefore, it was worthwhile to study the cardiovascular effects of other compounds also. Here α, α -bis (3-aminopropyl) malondipropylamide (P₁) and α, α -bis (3-aminopropyl) malondibutylamide (P₂) have been subjected to pharmacological screening.

Results and Discussions

The experiments were carried out on cats and frogs.

Effect on cat's blood pressure and heart rate: Compound P₁ produced a transient fall in blood pressure of cat at a dose of 15/kg intravenous. The duration of fall was about three to 5 min.

TABLE 1—ALKYL AND ARYLSUBSTITUTED MALONDIAMIDES

Sl. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M. P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd
1.	Malonodimethylamide	C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	134.0	76.90	21.52	21.53
2.	Malondiethylamide	C ₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₅	149.0	61.60	17.80	17.72
3.	Malondipropylamide	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	139.0	63.60	15.00	15.05
4.	Malondibutylamide	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	132.5	50.60	13.20	13.07
5.	Malondiisobutylamide	C ₁₁ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	126.5	63.60	13.14	13.07
6.	Malondibenzylamide	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	120.0	71.20	10.00	9.93

TABLE 2— α, α , BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) MALONDI (R) AMIDES

Sl. No.	Compound	Molecular formula	M. P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd
1.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malonodimethylamide	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅	125	55.50	23.80	23.72
2.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondiethylamide	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅	140	56.00	21.20	21.21
3.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondipropylamide	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅	82	56.20	19.00	19.10
4.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondibutylamide	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₅	125	54.00	17.45	17.50
5.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondiisobutylamide	C ₁₇ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₅	115	47.30	17.60	17.50
6.	α, α -bis-(β -cyanoethyl) malondibenzylamide	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₅	110	73.10	14.50	14.43

TABLE 3— α, α -BIS (3-AMINOPROPYL) MALONDIALKYLAMIDE

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	Methyl	C ₁₁ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	142	61.2	22.9	22.95
2.	Ethyl	C ₁₃ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₂	138	64.6	20.52	20.58
3.	Propyl	C ₁₅ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₂	130	66.6	18.68	18.66
4.	Butyl	C ₁₇ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₂	121	76.9	17.1	17.07

TABLE-4 α . AMINOMETHYL, α, α -BIS (AMINOPROPYL) (R) AMIDE

Sl. No.	R	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	Methyl	C ₁₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O	190	77.7	25.98	25.92
2.	Ethyl	C ₁₁ H ₂₆ N ₄ O	82	65.2	24.35	24.34

The blood pressure fall with a dose of 5 mg/kg was very little but 15 mg/kg i.v. produced a fall of about 30 mm of Hg. (Fig. A). During the effect of compound cardiac rate comes down from 102/min. to 80/min. in the cat. Compound P₂ showed no significant effect on blood pressure of cat in doses of 15 mg/kg i.v.

Fig. A. Shows the effect of compound P₁ and P₂ on Cat blood pressure.

Fig. B. Shows the effect of compound P₁ and P₂ on Frog's heart.

Effect on frog's heart: Compound P₁ caused a reduction in the force of contraction of frog's heart and compound P₂ caused a slowing in the rate of heart beat per minute (Fig. B). There was no effect on the force of contraction by compound P₂. Both compounds were given in doses of 5 mg. in the frog's heart.

Conclusion

Compound P₁ had a short lived hypotensive and negative chronotropic effect on cat's blood pressure and heart respectively. Compound P₂ had no significant effect on cat's blood pressure. P₁ had a negative inotropic effect on frog's heart, whereas P₂ produced a negative chronotropic effect on frog's heart.

Though these compounds have shown some activity of interest, more detailed studies will be necessary for evaluating their therapeutic importance and structure activity relationship.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to express their thanks to Head of Chemistry Department, Lucknow University for providing facilities and also to Dr. J. P. Berthwal for screening of the compounds. One of us (P.B.) is grateful to I.C.M.R., New Delhi for the grant of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. BERGER and DOLE, *J. Physiol.*, 1910, 41, 19.
2. DUNKER and HARTUNG, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1941, 30, 619.
3. B. ROHRMANN and H. A. SHOULE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1516.
4. R.F. NYSTROM and W. G. BROWNE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3738.
5. L. H. AMUNDSEN and L. S. NELSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 242.
6. A. E. FINHOLT and A. C. BOND, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 1199.